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Student activation in curriculum „Physics for engineers“

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ABSTRACT

Student activation is a major concern in any university lecture. Here, we report on our approach to shift the focus to understanding physics concepts in introductory physics courses for engineers at the Technische Universität Berlin. This course is divided into two independent parts: 'classical physics' and 'modern physics', being visited by 300 and 600 students, respectively, and are offered in a one-year term. Our new setup includes an interactive lecture, which is grouped into a traditional lecture, where the 'first exposure' occurs, the demonstration of most important experiments by the lecturer and sessions with concept tests related to the topic, i.e. Mazur's peer instruction, realized with an audience response system. A second major innovation are the flipped classroom practical sessions for which a complete new set of exercises was developed. These include concept tests and conceptual tasks connecting historic experiments, also shown in the lecture or tutorial classes, with theory, real-world phenomena and applications. The weekly exercises are provided online via the university's Moodle and include introductory texts and storytelling to connect topics and illustrate the relevance. During the flipped sessions, students form small groups, discussing and solving complex problems and conceptual questions, while instructors circulate from group to group to help, promote discussions and provide feedback. Understanding concepts of physics is solidified by discussions about the new concept tests and exercises and via conducting experiments in weekly tutorials with groups of 5 to 30 participants.

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1 BACKGROUND AND STARTING POINT

At the Technische Universität Berlin, Germany, we are working to reform two introductory physics courses for engineering majors. Starting in summer 2017, we established several research-based approaches to shift the focus of the courses to understanding physical concepts, including

- interactive engagement techniques, which can activate students and lead to higher learning outcomes [1] and
- addressing conceptual misunderstandings of natural phenomena [2].

The introductory physics course for engineering students is divided into two individual parts: 'classical physics' and 'modern physics', for which up to 300 and 600 students register, respectively. Each course is offered in a one-year term and is part of the curricula of at least twelve bachelor degree engineering majors, partly as a compulsory, partly as an elective compulsory subject or as extracurricular studies, see Fig. 1. Students in the first and second semesters make up the majority of participants. The courses consist of a lecture, small tutorial classes and flipped classroom sessions, each of which 90 minutes long, being offered weekly, and each course takes one semester, i.e. 14 weeks. The common learning objective of the courses is to study the fundamentals of physics in the following branches: classical mechanics, electromagnetism, classical optics and thermodynamics within the classical physics course, and atomic physics, an introduction to quantum mechanics, nuclear physics and solid-state physics within the modern physics course. The goal is that the students get to know the basic experiments, understand the corresponding theory and concepts and are able to apply them to problems. Previously, teaching of theory and concepts has been mainly the task of the lecture (passive learning), supported by the demonstration of

Fig. 1. (a) and (b) show the relative number of participants for the four programs that make up the largest groups within the modern and classical physics course, respectively. (c) shows the proportions of students divided according to their semester and their gender. The statistics are based on surveys carried out in 2018/19.

key experiments and interactive simulations. The content was practiced solely using exercise sheets in large tutorial classes, using algebra-based textbook questions where theory is applied to determine a quantitative value of a parameter. The course was concluded with a written exam, which mainly contained variants of those textbook questions, resulting in learning outcomes which have been observed by many lecturers [3, 4]: Most students memorize formulas useful to solve a particular type of problem, combine them and plug it into their calculator. They are often unable to explain the conceptual basis behind their own solutions to problems and cannot transfer their understanding to problems that deviate from standard textbook questions.

2 INTERACTIVE ENGAGEMENT TECHNIQUES

To shift the emphasis of both courses to conceptual understanding, we reformed several key components of the courses and implemented a combination of new types of exercises and methods. Another major concern is the incorporation of active learning to avert student passivity. It is still a challenge to encourage students to participate and learn continuously, as there is no attendance requirement for the lecture or the tutorial classes. Students register solely for the final exam. We evaluate the courses and in particular the new elements biannually in order to adapt and improve them.

In doing so, we focused on the advancement of the lecture and the development of flipped classroom sessions, since we have no possibility to change the structure of the courses as such and no additional teaching staff is needed. In contrast to usual flipped classroom approaches, we therefore have two complementary types of teaching methods, where the flipped classroom sessions deepen and practice the contents of the lecture. The small tutorials with 5 to 30 participants are led and prepared by undergraduate teaching assistants and remain as they were. About 20 of these tutorials are run on a weekly basis and have a flexible structure. Their topics are based on the current lecture and the students demands. In addition, a mandatory set of key experiments is carried out and discussed. The tutorials benefit also from the new concept tests in lecture and the new weekly exercises, as explained below.

2.1 The lecture

Our new setup incorporates interactive learning sessions as well as elements of a traditional physics lecture: Short introductions to a topic by the lecturer alternate with demonstrations of the most important experiments, being either shown live by the lecturer or as a simulation, and sessions with conceptual questions related to the topic. The latter is inspired by Mazur's peer instruction [5], realized with the open-source audience response system PINGO developed by the Universität Paderborn, Germany [6]. For example, concept tests are conducted at the beginning or end of a topic in order to clarify its relevance and stimulate discussion. Others are coupled to typical experiments linked to central physical phenomena.

For both courses, we created a repository of concept tests based on existing conceptual tests, syllabi and observations of students in problem-solving sessions. This allows the lecturer of 'classical physics' course to do several multiple choice questions per lecture, however, creating suitable questions for modern physics course is more difficult. All the materials used during the lecture, simulations and concept tests are provided online via the university's Moodle platform (<https://moodle.org/>).

2.2 The flipped classroom sessions

Another major approach in promoting conceptual understanding and reasoning are the flipped classroom practical sessions. Here we have moved away from a large tutorial classes in which algebra-based textbook tasks were solved and partly worked out by the teaching staff to a flipped classroom model. To do this, we have developed a completely new exercise that is provided to the students via the university's Moodle on a weekly basis. The students are encouraged to deal with the contents at home and to also attend the sessions not only by advertising their value but by making the exercises sufficiently difficult to solve for most students. During this weekly session, students form small groups discussing and solving complex problems as well as conceptual tasks. In addition, problem-solving strategies and supplementary material based on the students' feedback are provided online, which is particularly helpful for students who cannot attend the flipped classroom sessions. The sessions are staffed by about eight undergraduate teaching assistants and two graduate teaching assistants, circulating from group to group, helping to figure out complex problems, drive discussions, recognize misconceptions and provide feedback.

2.3 The exercises

For the courses, we developed a completely new set of exercises connecting the most important historical experiments, also shown in lecture or tutorial, with theory, real-world phenomena and relevant applications. We incorporated at least one application or phenomenon for each major concept. In addition, we provide introductions and cross-references to new and related topics, respectively, which motivates students to self-study and deepen their knowledge.

The understanding of the theory and the corresponding concepts is not only promoted by tasks and experiments, they are also partly linked by storytelling. Storytelling can humanize the teaching and learning of physics, helping students to memorize and understand the problem situation from which physical concepts first arose [7, 8]. This is particularly useful in modern physics, where the student can easily be guided from topic to topic, starting with the radical developments in physics starting in the early 20th century. In classical physics, understanding can be improved very effectively via typical concept tests and conceptual questions addressing common misconceptions. We also introduced weekly self-tests based on typical exam questions, which helps the students to test their knowledge by themselves.

We switched from algebra-based to more calculus-based exercises. Simple problems are mixed with complex ones depending on the topic, since no correlations should be unnecessarily simplified. For complex numeric exercises strategies are explained which help the students to solve the problem step by step, improving the problem-solving performance. This includes also small digressions into topics such as special relativity, quantum mechanics, particle physics, which link the knowledge of the students with other branches of physics and more recent discoveries and applications.

2.4 The exam

Students register themselves to the written exam (120 minutes) at the end of a semester. We developed a new setup of the exam for both courses in 2017 which comprises a mixture of algebra-based problems, concept tests and conceptual tasks,

where students write a short text, drawing a sketch or a graph. The written exam is practiced during the semester by means of two exemplary tests during the flipped classroom sessions.

3 EVALUATION AND EXAM PERFORMANCE

In order to obtain feedback regarding the course from the students, data was collected via a survey with 28 questions conducted biannually taking 10 - 15 minutes to complete. Fig. 2 shows an analysis of five questions that were asked within the last two semesters. Questions V1 and V2 refer to the concept tests that were presented in the lecture, we asked: "The concept tests are helpful to master the content." (V1) and "The discussion after the concept questions within the lecture promotes understanding" (V2). 82% and 71% of the students agreed to V1 for the modern and classical physics course, respectively, indicating that the concept tests are helpful to the students. Only 68% and 64%, respectively, agreed to question V2, which shows that the discussion part within the presentation can be improved.

Questions U1, U2 and U3 refer to the flipped classroom sessions, here we asked: "The explanations of the instructors are helpful to understand the content." (U1). 73% and 84% have agreed to this statement for modern and classical physics. Other questions were: "How much time in hours do you need to complete the weekly exercises?" (U2)

Fig. 2. The results for five exemplary questions asked during the last modern physics (blue) and classical physics (red) courses in 2018/19. The rating scale is 1 - 4, where 1 means "strongly agree" and 4 "strongly disagree." The mean value is indicated by m and n denotes the sample size.

and "How often did you attend the flipped classroom sessions during the semester?" (U3), where the majority needs on average four hours to complete the exercises. The results are very similar for the two courses, which shows a good agreement in the difficulty of the exercises, although the topics and the types of tasks vary greatly. Question U3 also shows almost identical results for the two courses, at least 82% of students attend the flipped classroom sessions more than seven times per semester. The surveys were carried out in the last third of each semester, which explains the low response rate.

We now turn to an analysis of the results of the exams carried out between the years 2016 and 2019. Fig. 3 a shows a plot of the mean of the score for the exams in a particular year m_i subtracted by the average score for the last years M

$$m_i - M = m_i - \frac{\sum_i m_i N^i}{\sum_i N^i}, \tag{1}$$

where i denotes the year and N^i the corresponding number of participants. Only those students who passed the exam are considered, the students who failed are accounted for by the failure rate. Since the reforms did not begin until 2017, the results of 2016 are the last we have been able to obtain and are serving as a reference. For the modern and classical physics courses we observe an increase in performance of 12% and 9% from '16 to '17, respectively. The failure rate has fallen particularly for the modern physics course, i.e. the difference is 24% between the years '16 and '19. For the classical physics course, the failure rates have fallen by 7% between the years '16 and '18. We note that the informative value of these statistics in relation to the 2016 data is low, as we have reformed not only the course but also the structure of the exams from 2017 onwards. Nevertheless, the performance, at least for the modern physics course, has increased considerably in the years '17 to '19 by 15%, whereas the performance for the classical physics course is around the average score M . This could

Fig. 3. (a) shows data of the exam performance for the modern physics exam (circles) and the classical physics exam (triangles) for the years '16 to '19. The value $m_i - M$ (blue axis) is the mean of the exam score m_i for a particular year i subtracted by the average score for the last years M . (b) depicts the individual exam performance subtracted by the mean m_{19} (blue circles) with regard to the attendance in the flipped classroom sessions for the 2019 exam. Red squares indicate the average values for each answer and n denotes the sample size.

also be related to the fact that classical physics, in contrast to modern physics, is a compulsory elective subject for most bachelor degree programs, see *Fig. 1 a* and *b*.

Fig. 3 b shows the individual exam performance in relation to the participation in the flipped classroom sessions. Here we asked a part of the students again the question U3. Here no clear Trent is discernible as the results are close to the mean, but on average those students who stated that they were always present completed about 4.5% more tasks correctly than those who were never present. This could be due to the fact that we make all of our content available on Moodle and also provide help to accomplish the tasks, so that many students work independently. In addition, many students attend the small tutorials where the content and the new exercises are discussed also.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We have reformed two major introductory physical courses for engineering students by integrating concept tests into the lecture and new exercises that are solved by the students in collaborative group work in flipped classroom sessions or by self-studying with emphasis on conceptual understanding, argumentation development and real-world phenomena. Our reforms include novel exams, exam training, self-tests and online material made available to students and teachers. Our initial assessments show that the innovations are well received and helpful and the exam performance was increased. We are now working on concept tests for modern physics and creating a library of exercises and concept tests that is constantly being improved and expanded. As a next step, we are solidifying and supporting the reforms, especially as the teaching staff and lecturers change with the semesters.

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